

CORPUS - BASED APPROACH TO LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *The report aims to describe the action research that took place to study the use of corpus – based approach in an ESL classroom. The author created a corpus using Sketch platform, and the topic of the corpus is “Food and Nutrition”. It was used to create several activities, which have been provided in the Appendix. In this action research 24 students at the upper – intermediate level participated and the majority of them found the approach engaging. The data was collected by interviewing the subjects after the study. According to the participants, the corpus can be applied best to learn collocations both in and outside the classroom.*

Keywords: *corpus, corpora, concordance.*

Introduction. Since language learning has become one of the main trends, a lot of attention has been paid to language teaching around the world. The need for learning languages and technology development encourages teachers to find modern ways of dealing with language problems. As a computer-based tool, corpus linguistics is focused on offering "a ready resource of natural, or authentic, texts for language acquisition (Reppen, 2010)." Johansson (2009) makes a solid case for the usefulness of corpora in language courses by demonstrating how it might influence exam preparation, textbooks, activities, and syllabus design. The use of corpora in language instruction can be a useful technique for teaching vocabulary, grammar, and language use to EFL learners (Dazdarevic et.al 2014).

The report aims to describe ways of introducing new vocabulary using a corpus-based approach to the topic “Food and nutrition”. Therefore, it first introduces the corpus, its type, and its usage, second, a quantitative analysis of the corpus is provided, third, limitations are noted, next it reports activities designed due to the corpus, and finally, reflects on the experience at the usage of those activities.

Methodology. The corpus was compiled in 2022, and it contains authentic materials including guidebooks on food and nutrition, several magazines, some professional articles and an encyclopedia on food, etc. The data come from the same point in the time (2010 - 2022), which makes the corpus synchronic. It is a written monolingual corpus consisting of a million words which are quite small for its type (O’Keefe, McCarthy, and Carter, 2007). The corpus was created to be used in an ESL classroom, however, it can be called a learner corpus. To be more precise, learner corpora include digital textual information of a language developed by foreign language learners (Pravec, 2002). It is a specialized corpus as it is limited to one topic area – food and nutrition. This corpus can also fulfil the needs of English for Specific Purposes learners as it serves the needs of ESP learners, for example, dieticians and nutritionists.

Corpora are most usually correlated with quantitative studies due to the simplicity with which frequency analysis can be generated (Timmis, 2015). The table (Figure 1) below illustrates the most frequent words in the corpus.

word (1,620 items | 122,800 total frequency)

Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency	Word	Frequency
1 and	37,001	14 associated	932	27 americans	553	40 against	328
2 a	17,151	15 a.	916	28 addition	535	41 ages	320
3 are	7,952	16 acids	914	29 available	507	42 absorption	317
4 as	6,319	17 after	874	30 added	495	43 alcohol	314
5 an	2,776	18 among	870	31 animals	469	44 african	313
6 al.	2,397	19 american	859	32 agriculture	424	45 around	313
7 also	2,337	20 although	859	33 amounts	417	46 assoc.	290
8 at	2,222	21 age	854	34 adolescents	388	47 additional	272
9 about	1,400	22 any	660	35 according	375	48 analysis	263
10 all	1,383	23 animal	647	36 aged	362	49 amino	235
11 am	1,279	24 amount	590	37 average	359	50 academy	225
12 adults	1,093	25 association	573	38 adequate	349		
13 acid	943	26 activity	556	39 another	345		

Figure 1. Food and Nutrition word frequency list.

Below frequency lists from the corpus are provided and consist of lemmas. Lemma is the basic word form (Timmis, 2015): for example, the lemma “eat” has the word forms eats, ate, and eating.

It can be seen that the most used lemmas (figure 2) are articles and prepositions. Also, it can be discovered that the materials used to build the corpus are mostly about health and diet; the word “study” indicates that there are some academic articles about studies too.

lemma (19,357 items | 939,263 total frequency)

Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency
1 the	37,433	14 as	6,319	27 not	3,482	40 effect	2,577
2 and	37,001	15 milk	6,299	28 vitamin	3,352	41 may	2,529
3 of	33,225	16 have	5,885	29 than	3,007	42 high	2,514
4 be	30,483	17 on	4,925	30 this	2,986	43 which	2,456
5 in	23,596	18 from	4,827	31 other	2,930	44 risk	2,454
6 a	19,659	19 intake	4,785	32 health	2,891	45 et	2,410
7 to	19,482	20 dairy	4,269	33 can	2,872	46 al.	2,397
8 that	8,805	21 diet	4,204	34 more	2,867	47 also	2,337
9 for	8,512	22 it	4,182	35 bone	2,817	48 they	2,318
10 food	7,759	23 by	3,944	36 dietary	2,780	49 mg	2,262
11 or	7,097	24 fat	3,842	37 blood	2,664	50 at	2,222
12 with	6,722	25 study	3,690	38 increase	2,646		
13 calcium	6,565	26 j.	3,491	39 use	2,643		

Figure 2. Food and Nutrition frequency list of lemmas.

Figure 3 demonstrates that the word “dietary” is used more than the word “healthy”, or see the difference between “significant” and “important”.

adjective (4,636 items | 102,681 total frequency)

Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency
1 dietary	2,714	14 small	784	27 available	507	40 early	418
2 other	2,581	15 less	753	28 sweet	505	41 nutritional	418
3 high	2,344	16 whole	737	29 different	485	42 significant	409
4 low	1,836	17 fatty	718	30 similar	477	43 first	395
5 more	1,731	18 low-fat	665	31 fresh	475	44 saturated	368
6 fat	1,489	19 large	663	32 young	474	45 daily	368
7 such	1,346	20 most	646	33 due	472	46 major	363
8 many	1,247	21 same	636	34 white	467	47 adequate	349
9 good	1,071	22 great	628	35 common	459	48 colorectal	349
10 total	870	23 important	616	36 few	456	49 red	348
11 healthy	848	24 human	562	37 clinical	441	50 soft	338
12 old	815	25 raw	550	38 american	427		
13 nutrient	795	26 several	519	39 beneficial	422		

Figure 3. Food and Nutrition frequency list of adjectives

The diagram below (figure 4) represents that the word “intake” is used four times more than “consumption”. Students can use it to make assumptions about the frequency of words or lemmas on a particular topic and can check the hypothesis using the frequency lists.

noun (13,322 items | 378,051 total frequency)

Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency
1 food	7,759	14 fat	2,328	27 fruit	1,587	40 source	1,183
2 calcium	6,565	15 mg	2,262	28 weight	1,571	41 consumption	1,169
3 milk	6,193	16 nutrition	2,096	29 lactose	1,562	42 nutrient	1,160
4 intake	4,785	17 cancer	2,078	30 chapter	1,505	43 foods	1,134
5 dairy	4,269	18 day	2,031	31 pressure	1,475	44 calorie	1,101
6 diet	4,110	19 body	1,964	32 nutr	1,436	45 group	1,098
7 study	3,617	20 year	1,912	33 cheese	1,421	46 vegetable	1,073
8 vitamin	3,352	21 protein	1,895	34 level	1,391	47 part	1,053
9 health	2,891	22 product	1,854	35 cholesterol	1,387	48 cup	1,006
10 bone	2,769	23 disease	1,796	36 page	1,365	49 amount	1,006
11 blood	2,661	24 child	1,781	37 water	1,254	50 factor	976
12 effect	2,570	25 woman	1,770	38 am	1,248		
13 risk	2,444	26 acid	1,728	39 adult	1,242		

Figure 4. Food and Nutrition frequency list of nouns.

verb (2,455 items | 122,444 total frequency)

Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency	Lemma	Frequency
1 be	30,481	14 serve	860	27 help	580	40 know	410
2 have	5,885	15 show	860	28 follow	551	41 take	404
3 increase	2,155	16 provide	847	29 produce	543	42 feed	399
4 use	2,002	17 compare	780	30 recommend	541	43 become	394
5 do	1,865	18 grow	780	31 prevent	533	44 give	381
6 reduce	1,738	19 cook	755	32 contribute	502	45 accord	379
7 consume	1,589	20 add	753	33 improve	459	46 influence	375
8 include	1,466	21 lead	660	34 decrease	454	47 meet	370
9 eat	1,464	22 need	651	35 suggest	454	48 report	363
10 find	1,445	23 indicate	616	36 demonstrate	429	49 vary	355
11 make	1,389	24 see	611	37 develop	427	50 consider	351
12 contain	1,150	25 call	584	38 come	426		
13 associate	936	26 age	582	39 randomize	426		

Figure 5. Food and Nutrition frequency list of verbs.

Using the list above (figure 5) learners can know the difference between the frequency of “eat” and “consume” or “provide” and “give”. They can be taught that in an academic context the words “consume” and “provide” are used more rather than their synonyms.

<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 : Promote health and reduce chronic diseases associated Decrease sodium intake (2,400 milligrams or with diet and weight less daily) Weight status and grow
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 rough health plans Nutrition counseling for medical conditions Increase fruit intake (2+ servings daily) Increase vegetable intake (3+ servings daily) Include nut
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 dical conditions Increase fruit intake (2+ servings daily) Increase vegetable intake (3+ servings daily) Include nutrition counseling in physician office visits Foor
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 on counseling in physician office visits Food security Increase grain product intake (6+ servings daily) Increase access to nutritionally adequate and safe foods
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 ase access to nutritionally adequate and safe foods Decrease saturated fat intake (less than 10% of calories) for an active, healthy life Decrease total fat intake
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 ttake (less than 10% of calories) for an active, healthy life Decrease total fat intake (no more than 30% of calories) *Nutrition and Overweight is one focus area
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 slight degree, so have deaths from some cancers. </s></s>On average, the intake of total fat and saturated fat has decreased.</s></s>Food labeling provides r
<input type="checkbox"/>	doc#0 at the recommended 5 servings of fruits and vegetables.</s></s>Overall, fat intake is decreasing (from 40 percent of calories in the late 1970s to 33 percent in i

Figure 6. Food and Nutrition concordance lines for the word “intake”.

Concordance lines above (figure 6) help to see how collocations of the word “intake” are employed together. O’Keeffe et al. (2007) describe it as a way ‘to find every occurrence of a

particular word or phrase' (Yilmaz and Soruc, 2014). Furthermore, the most frequent collocates which occur within two or three words can be seen using concordance lines.

According to Jones and Durrant (2010), three essential points should be taken into consideration while applying the word frequency lists in the pedagogic context, it implies that:

1. The corpus "Food and Nutrition" is only for writing reports and should not be applied to speaking activities. The word frequency might be irrelevant for British English or other specific learners as most of the journals are by American publishers.
2. The frequency lists generated above are about lemmas; however, words can also be treated similarly.
3. While creating activities for students, polysemous words were not dealt with since the essential meanings of the lemmas were used.

Although there are a lot of various uses of the corpus, the limitations should also be noted. First, the corpus is formed to assist students to write about their diet, therefore, it includes mainly scientific articles and magazines. It does not benefit those who desire to see the frequency of a specific term in informal situations. Second, it is only for high intermediate and advanced level learners, and cannot be applied to elementary or low intermediate classes.

Discussion. According to this corpus, seven activities (See the Appendix) were designed for upper – intermediate ESL learners aged 17-18. The final learning outcome of the lesson is that students should be able to use the new vocabulary in practice. The main aim of the activities is to enable students to be familiar with the collocations and to use them in future report writing tasks. The writing task should include the collocations of discovering the corpus and/or can be assigned as homework. The activities offer the learners an opportunity to exploit the corpus directly, which enables Data-Driven Learning (DDL). Within the CLT paradigm, vocabulary learning is shifting away from teaching individual words and toward exposing students to lexical elements in authentic and relevant situations (Balunda, 2009). When compared to typical vocabulary teaching approaches such as consulting a dictionary, viewing concordance lines has been shown to result in tiny but constant gains in students' vocabulary knowledge, improved recall, and the learning of transferrable word knowledge (Balunda, 2009). The beauty of using DDL is in its autonomy as learners can discover new topics for themselves (Boulton, 2009). The designed activities for this corpus can be utilized either in the classroom or assigned as homework. The data can be reached by accessing the corpus directly or printing them and distributing them during the lesson. All activities can be done by deriving the hypothesis and testing them against further data which makes them researchers (Johns, 1991; Aston, 2001). It gives the opportunity for learner autonomy, and the classroom becomes less teacher-centralized (Gilquin et al., 2010). The activities cover the main collocations that need to be learned on the topic "Food and nutrition", and these are word phrases with "protein", "carb", "fat", "consume", "nutrition", "food", "intake" and "eat". Types of the activities are gap-filling, guessing, and making sentences, and mostly require quantitative analysis of the corpus. However, the last activity can be an example of qualitative analysis of corpus when other larger corpora such as BNC or COCA are used to compare the data.

Conclusion. Reflecting on the experience at the usage of the activities several things should be noted. The corpus was introduced in two upper - intermediate classes; both classes received the activities in printed forms. Out of 24 students almost 80 % were curious about the approach they found new. The rest of the learners described it as "time – consuming". More than half of the students created a new corpus to compile written essays on other topics to see the most frequent

collocations. The majority of the learners liked the concordance lines as they offered to compile a corpus of listening transcripts of their course book. One of them noted that it would be great to see the forms of collocations in the context. The usage of the corpus caused the students to become curiosity – driven learners (Aston, 2001). By the end of the lesson, the students developed reports including the collocations.

The need for new ways of learning and teaching languages is increasing, therefore, employing corpus – based approach in a pedagogical context can lead to students' success. This report tried to describe the appliance of the corpus designed for B2 level learners on the topic "Food and Nutrition". Although there were several benefits of using the particular corpus, some limitations were observed too. The activities designed were to introduce vocabulary only, however, it would be a better idea to integrate some grammar focused activities. I believe that in the future, a corpus-based approach to teaching will become one of the most applicable.

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